

Local varieties Malbhog, Pokikoli, Silguti, Gajep sali 1, and Sarusokua suffered 15-20% leaf damage (see table). Nonpreference for feeding may be the resistance mechanism in these varieties. This study confirmed that glutinous rice varieties are less preferred by hispa. ■

Resistance of selected rice varieties to brown planthopper (BPH) and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH)

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The important rice pests in China—BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål and WBPH *Sogatellafurcifera* Horváth—usually occur together. Many varieties resistant to planthoppers have been released, and the threat of BPH and WBPH outbreaks significantly reduced. We evaluated damage, fecundity, and population dynamics of BPH and WBPH on some widely cultivated rice varieties, using the seedling screening technique in the glasshouse.

Xu-Shui 620 and Bing 664 were resistant to BPH but moderately resistant and moderately susceptible, respectively, to WBPH. Shan-You No. 6 was resistant to BPH but susceptible to WBPH. Both Shan-You 63 and Xiu-Shui 48 were susceptible to both BPH and WBPH.

In the ovipositing test, a pair of newly emerged BPH or WBPH adults were

Population dynamics of the brown planthopper (BPH) and the whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) on select on rice varieties in ricefields, Hangzhou, China, 1990.

introduced into test tubes containing one plant of a variety. Plants were replaced every 2 d and the number of eggs laid counted.

At tillering and booting, the BPH female laid significantly more eggs on Shan-You 63 and Xiu-Shui 48 than on other varieties, but BPH fecundity at booting was higher than at tillering (see table). Shan-You No. 6, Shan-You 63, and Xiu-Shui 48 received more WBPH eggs than Bing 664 and Xiu-Shui 620 at tillering, but at booting, significantly fewer WBPH eggs were laid on all varieties.

In a field survey, Xiu-Shui 620, Shan-You No. 6, and Bing 664 had lower BPH populations than Shan-You 63, and Xiu-Shui 48. The number of BPH increased gradually with plant age, but the number of WBPH decreased rapidly with plant

age after 73 d old. This seems to be due to the decline in fecundity of WBPH after booting (see figure).

Japonica variety Xiu-Shui 620 appears to be most valuable as a BPH and WBPH resistance donor. ■

Stress tolerance—adverse soils

Rice genotypes with tolerance for low available phosphorus in Sierra Leone soils

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Soils in Sierra Leone are low activity clay type and low in available P. Inadequate P retards growth and development of rice. Identification of genotypes tolerant of low available P will assist breeders and farmers in minimizing adverse effects of P deficiency.

In 1989-90, we screened 294 local rices collected in 1988 for tolerance for low available P. In the uplands, 72 accessions of *O. glaberrima* and 72 of *O. sativa* were tested with and without P; in the inland valley swamp, 70 accessions of *O. glaberrima* and 80 of *O. sativa* were evaluated.

Damage and fecundity of BPH and WBPH on selected rice varieties.^a Hangzhou, China, 1989.

Variety	Damage rating ^b		Fecundity of BPH ^c (eggs/female in 8 d)		Fecundity of WBPH ^c (eggs/female in 8 d)	
	BPH	WBPH	Tillering	Booting	Tillering	Booting
Shan-You No. 6	1.3	9.0	51.2 bc	79.2 b	112.7 ab	92.8 a
Shan-You 63	8.7	9.0	74.5 b	139.9 a	138.6 a	86.0 a
Xiu-Shui 620	1.0	3.7	56.0 bc	78.5 b	77.4 b	69.9 a
Bing 664	2.3	5.7	34.9 c	62.9 b	82.7 b	74.6 a
XU-Shui 48	9.0	8.0	128.9 a	132.0 a	126.5 a	93.0 a
Rathu Heenati (resistant check)	1.0	1.3	22.4 c	28.6 c	12.4 c	10.1 b
TN1 (susceptible check)	9.0	9.0	113.2 ab	125.6 a	104.8 ab	88.4 a

^aSeparation of means in a column by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level. ^bBy the Standard evaluation system for rice.

^cAv of 2 replications.